

Artificial neural network modelling of biogas production from vinasse

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RESUMO – Artificial neural network (ANN) models to predict biogas production and chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal during the digesting of vinasse were developed. Experimental data from the literature were used for developing feedforward neural networks. The data were grouped into three subsets: training, test, and validation. Twenty different ANN topologies were evaluated by varying the number of neurons, the activation function, and the training algorithm. The best ANN model ($R^2 = 0.9990$) includes using 15 neurons, tansing as a transfer function, and trainlm as a training algorithm. The results indicate that the ANN model can be used for forecasting and optimising biogas production from vinasse.

1 INTRODUCTION

Global needs for energy and environmental effects associated with the use of fossil fuels have increased the demand for biofuels. Among the most used biofuels in the world, ethanol stands out. In 2018, the U.S. had 210 biorefineries producing around 61 billion litres of corn ethanol (RFA, 2019). Brazil is the second-largest ethanol producer in the world, having produced 33.1 billion litres of sugarcane ethanol in the 2018/2019 harvest (CONAB, 2019).

In Brazil, sugarcane is the raw material mainly used for ethanol production, with a 2018/19 crop of 620.41 million tons (CONAB, 2019). About 45% of Brazilian mills process more than 2 million tons of sugarcane per year and produce approximately 80 litres of ethanol per ton of sugarcane (EMBRAPA, 2020). Sugarcane is converted into ethanol by sucrose fermentation, thus generating significant amounts of vinasse (10 to 15 litres of vinasse per litre of ethanol). The composition of the vinasse includes organic acids, glycerol, and sugars. Due to this composition, vinasse can be converted into high-added-value products, such as biogas via anaerobic digestion.

Some researchers have employed neural networks for modelling the production of biogas using a plurality of substrates and operational conditions. For instance, Ghatak *et al.* (2018) and Almomani (2020) evaluated various temperatures (35 to 55 °C) and reported that the employed neural networks predicted the production of biogas with high accuracy. Dibaba *et al.* (2016) modelled the biogas production from beet vinasse using neural networks to correlate the parameters of chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal, total suspended solids (TSS), volatile fatty acids (VFA), and biogas production.

Although several studies have been undertaken on the prediction of biogas production, however, information on the biogas production and COD removal from vinasse appears to be scanty in the literature. The main objective of this work was to develop an ANN model capable of predicting biogas production and COD removal considering operational parameters (e.g., reaction time, temperature, reactor volume).

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection

Data were collected from 30 studies from the literature on the anaerobic digestion of vinasse including the following operational parameters: vinasse COD, feed COD, vinasse type, reactor type, reaction temperature, OLR, reactor volume, and HRT. Data were further processed for eliminating potential outliers. All collected data were treated as input variables. Meanwhile, biogas production and COD removal were selected as output variables.

2.2 Artificial neural networks (ANNs)

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) include four main parts: an input matrix, a hidden layer, an output layer, and an output matrix. ANNs can be constructed with different topologies, varying the number of neurons, the activation function of neurons, and the network-training algorithm. In this work, ANN models were developed using the *neural networking toolbox* (*nntool*) from MATLAB®. The experimental planning used to find the best ANN model is shown in Table 1.

To find the best topology of the neural network, activation functions used in neurons were *logsig* and *tansig*. Equations (1) and (2) represent these functions:

$$\log sig(x) = 1/(1 + e^{-x}) \quad (1)$$

$$\tan sig(x) = (1/(2 + e^{-2x})) - 1 \quad (2)$$

Two training algorithms for ANNs were also tested: Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation (*Trainlm*) and Bayesian Regularisation (*Trainbr*). On the one hand, the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm is considered faster and more efficient. On the other hand, Bayesian Regularisation's main characteristic is to achieve convergence when the sum of squared errors (SSE) and the sum of squared weights (SSW) are relatively constant over many iterations, which enables obtaining results with a reduced amount of data.

Table 1: Structure of a neural network suitable for the prediction of methane production and COD removal

Number	Neuron	Activation function	Training algorithm
1	8	Logsig	Trainbr
2	10	Logsig	Trainbr
3	15	Logsig	Trainbr
4	20	Logsig	Trainbr
5	30	Logsig	Trainbr
6	8	Tansig	Trainbr
7	10	Tansig	Trainbr

8	15	Tansig	Trainbr
9	20	Tansig	Trainbr
10	30	Tansig	Trainbr
11	8	Logsig	Trainlm
12	10	Logsig	Trainlm
13	15	Logsig	Trainlm
14	20	Logsig	Trainlm
15	30	Logsig	Trainlm
16	8	Tansig	Trainlm
17	10	Tansig	Trainlm
18	15	Tansig	Trainlm
19	20	Tansig	Trainlm
20	30	Tansig	Trainlm

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 ANN topologies

Table 2 presents the coefficient of determination (R^2) for each topology proposed in Table 1 for methane production (output). The best results of the ANN topology for methane prediction involved the *trainlm* training algorithm (exp. 11-20). Among them, experiment number 18 used the topology 4-15-1-1, which means 4 input variables, 15 neurons within the hidden layer with the *tansig* transfer function, 1 neuron in the output layer with linear transfer function and 1 output variable with *trainlm* training algorithm. This setup had the best result for the four coefficients of determination (see Figure 1), which all are greater than 0.9996.

Table 2: R^2 for training, validation, test, and all (all data) groups associated with the 20 ANN topologies for methane production.

Number	Training	Validation	Test	All
1	0.4349	0.6925	0.3986	0.4962
2	0.5265	0.9986	0.1707	0.4652
3	0.4758	0.9862	0.5101	0.5171
4	0.4031	0.9894	0.6739	0.5132
5	0.4530	0.3239	0.9374	0.5239
6	0.6109	0.4302	0.7086	0.5196
7	0.5982	0.8065	0.2837	0.5008
8	0.5985	0.7872	0.6800	0.5187
9	0.4958	0.6705	0.7753	0.5183
10	0.4785	0.6225	0.7669	0.4325

11	0.9439	0.9733	0.9986	0.9185
12	0.8249	0.9974	0.9971	0.8637
13	0.9485	0.9931	0.9991	0.9545
14	0.9981	0.9476	0.9999	0.8954
15	0.9770	0.9665	0.9959	0.9376
16	0.9839	0.9551	0.9995	0.9452
17	0.9858	0.9965	0.9984	0.9842
18	0.9997	0.9999	0.9996	0.9997
19	0.9948	0.9971	0.9907	0.9829
20	0.9207	0.9989	0.9911	0.9317

Figure 1 presents the data of the neural network with topology (4-15-1-1, experiment 18), which shows a good fit for the four data sets. The values of R^2 close to 1 indicate a good prediction for methane production.

Figure 1: R^2 values of experiment 18 for methane production

In the case of COD removal, experiment 18 (4-15-1-1 topology) also showed the best results (not shown here) with a R^2 value of 0.9993.

The weights and biases, calculated by the network, were used to calculate the values of methane production and COD removal by the ANN model and to compare those values with the experimental data.

3.2 ANN for predicting methane production and COD removal

The proposed ANN was tested to predict the two output variables combined in one ANN. The topology selected for this model was substantially similar to the one used in experiment 18, but with 2 outputs (4-15-2-2), with the tansig transfer function in the first layer, linear transfer function in the output layer, and trainlm as the training algorithm. Figure 2 shows the R^2 values for the four data sets.

Figure 2: R^2 values using a 4-15-2-2 ANN topology for methane production and COD removal.

In Figure 2, the 4-15-2-2 topology fits well with the data set resulting in R^2 values greater than 0.9992 for all cases. In addition, the two data groups' formation is because the methane production data ranges from 0 to 0.40 and the COD removal data ranges from 0.60 to 1. Consequently, the prediction made by the ANN may not be as accurate as in the first two cases. The data on methane production and COD removal obtained by ANN simulation were plotted with the experimental data in Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows a comparison between the methane production and COD removal predicted by the ANN model (red and black lines, respectively) and experimental data (green and cyan lines) from the literature. Both cases exhibited a very good agreement with the experimental data. The R^2 value is 0.9990.

The results found were better than those reported by Rego *et al.* (2019) ($R^2 = 0.7770$) and Dibaba *et al.* (2016) ($R^2 = 0.9210$). However, it is worth noting that the substrates, the bio digestion parameters, and the configuration of the neural network used were different from those used in this work.

Figure 3: Experimental data versus ANN data using the 4-15-2-2 topology for methane production and COD removal.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Artificial neural network (ANN) models to predict biogas production and chemical oxygen demand (COD) removal during the digesting of vinasse were developed. Experimental data from the literature were used for developing and comparing the ANN models. Twenty different ANN topologies were evaluated by varying the number of neurons, the activation function, and the training algorithm. The best ANN model includes 15 neurons, tansing as the transfer function, and trainlm as the training algorithm. The predicted methane production and COD removal using the ANN model showed a very good agreement with the experimental data. The ANN model could be a useful tool for process exploration and optimisation of biogas production from vinasse.

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